

Sophie Germain Primes and the Totient of Fibonacci Numbers

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Abstract

We study the set $S(q)$ of residue classes r modulo the Pisano period $\pi(q)$ for which $q \mid \varphi(F_m)$ for every $m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}$. We prove that if q is a Sophie Germain prime and $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$, then $S(q)$ is a nonempty arithmetic progression of odd cardinality, and that every such prime $q > 5$ satisfies $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$. Conversely, we show that if a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ has $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, then necessarily $p = 2q+1$, so q is Sophie Germain. We conjecture that $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ forces the existence of such a prime p ; this is verified for all $q \leq 50,000$. Unconditionally, the infinitude of Sophie Germain primes implies the existence of infinitely many primes $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$ with $(2q+1) \mid F_{\pi(q)}$ —a purely Fibonacci-theoretic condition. These results generalize to arbitrary Lucas sequences $U_n(P, Q)$ with non-square discriminant.

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1 Introduction

The arithmetic of Fibonacci numbers has been an active area of research for over a century. Among the central themes are the distribution of prime factors of F_m , periodicity of Fibonacci sequences modulo integers, and the interaction of F_m with classical multiplicative functions such as Euler's totient φ .

For a prime p , the rank of apparition $z(p)$ is the smallest positive integer k with $p \mid F_k$; it is well-defined for every prime p [3, 6]. The Pisano period $\pi(n)$ is the period of $(F_m \pmod{n})$. Both quantities satisfy well-known divisibility relations: $z(q) \mid \pi(q)$ and $\pi(q) \mid q^2 - 1$ for every odd prime q [6].

Definition 1.1. *For an odd prime q , let*

$$S(q) = \{r \pmod{\pi(q)} : q \mid \varphi(F_m) \text{ for all } m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}\}.$$

The set $S(q)$ collects those residue classes modulo $\pi(q)$ that guarantee divisibility of $\varphi(F_m)$ by q . Since the definition quantifies over all m in each residue class, $S(q)$ is well-defined as a subset of $\mathbb{Z}/\pi(q)\mathbb{Z}$.

Main results

Our results are as follows.

- (i) **Sufficient criterion** (Theorem 3.1). If a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ has $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, then every multiple of $z(p)$ modulo $\pi(q)$ lies in $S(q)$.
- (ii) **Sophie Germain sufficient condition** (Theorem 4.1). If q is a Sophie Germain prime and $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$, then $S(q) \neq \emptyset$.
- (iii) **Uniqueness of the witnessing prime** (Theorem 4.2). If a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ satisfies $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, then $p = 2q + 1$, so q is Sophie Germain.
- (iv) **Converse conjecture** (Conjecture 4.4). $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ implies the existence of a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$. Verified for all $q \leq 50,000$.
- (v) **Arithmetic progression structure** (Theorem 5.1). For a Sophie Germain prime q with $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$, $S(q)$ is an arithmetic progression in $\mathbb{Z}/\pi(q)\mathbb{Z}$ with $|S(q)| = \pi(q)/z(2q+1)$.
- (vi) **Legendre symbols and parity** (Theorems 6.1, 6.2 and Lemma 6.3). For a Sophie Germain prime $q > 5$ with $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$: $\left(\frac{5}{2q+1}\right) = -1$, $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = -1$, $\pi(q) \mid 2(q+1)$, and $|S(q)|$ is odd.
- (vii) **Congruence constraint** (Theorem 7.1). For a Sophie Germain prime $q > 5$ with $S(q) \neq \emptyset$: $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$.
- (viii) **Sophie Germain reformulation** (Corollary 7.2). The infinitude of Sophie Germain primes implies the existence of infinitely many primes $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$ with $(2q+1) \mid F_{\pi(q)}$. Assuming Conjecture 4.4, the converse holds.

2 Preliminaries

Standard references are Wall [6], Carmichael [3], and Lucas [4]; see also the textbook [7].

Lemma 2.1 (Basic properties of z and π). *Let p be a prime and q an odd prime.*

- (a) $p \mid F_m$ if and only if $z(p) \mid m$.
- (b) $z(q) \mid \pi(q)$ and $\pi(q) \mid q^2 - 1 = (q-1)(q+1)$.
- (c) If $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = +1$ then $z(p) \mid p-1$.
- (d) If $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$ then $z(p) \mid p+1$.
- (e) If $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = +1$ then $\pi(q) \mid q-1$. If $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = -1$ then $\pi(q) \mid 2(q+1)$.

Proof. Part (a) is [6, §2]. Part (b) is [6, Theorems 6 and 7]. Parts (c) and (d): the characteristic polynomial $x^2 - x - 1$ of the Fibonacci recurrence factors over \mathbb{F}_{p^2} ; its roots α, β satisfy $\alpha\beta = -1$. When $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = +1$, $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times$, giving $z(p) \mid p - 1$. When $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$, $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^2} \setminus \mathbb{F}_p$ and Frobenius gives $\alpha^p = \beta$, so $\alpha^{p+1} = \alpha\beta = -1$ and $z(p) \mid p + 1$. (This sharpens $z(p) \mid 2(p+1)$; see [5, 6].) Part (e): the Pisano period equals the order of the matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ in $\text{GL}_2(\mathbb{F}_q)$. When $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = +1$, this matrix is diagonalizable over \mathbb{F}_q with eigenvalue order dividing $q - 1$. When $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = -1$, the eigenvalues lie in $\mathbb{F}_{q^2} \setminus \mathbb{F}_q$ with $\alpha^{q+1} = -1$, giving $\pi(q) \mid 2(q + 1)$. See [4, 6]. \square

Remark. *The sharpened statement $z(p) \mid p + 1$ when $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$ is essential for the proof of Theorem 4.2.*

Lemma 2.2 ([6, 5]). *Let p be an odd prime with $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$. Then $v_2(z(p)) = v_2(p + 1)$.*

Lemma 2.3 (Totient divisibility). *Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ be a prime with $p \mid F_m$. Then $q \mid \varphi(F_m)$.*

Proof. Since $p \mid F_m$, multiplicativity of φ gives $(p - 1) \mid \varphi(F_m)$. As $q \mid p - 1$, the result follows. \square

3 Characterization of $S(q)$

Theorem 3.1. *For an odd prime q ,*

$$\{r \bmod \pi(q) : \exists \text{ prime } p \equiv 1 \pmod{q} \text{ with } z(p) \mid \gcd(r, \pi(q))\} \subseteq S(q).$$

In particular, $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ whenever there exists a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$.

Proof. Let r belong to the left-hand side: there exists a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ with $z(p) \mid \gcd(r, \pi(q))$. For any $m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}$, since $z(p) \mid r$ and $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, we get $z(p) \mid m$, so $p \mid F_m$ (Lemma 2.1(a)), so $q \mid \varphi(F_m)$ (Lemma 2.3). As this holds for every such m , $r \in S(q)$. \square

4 The Sophie Germain connection

Theorem 4.1 (Sufficient condition). *Let q be a Sophie Germain prime with $p = 2q + 1$. If $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, then $S(q) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. Since $p = 2q + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ and $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, Theorem 3.1 gives $0 \in S(q)$, so $S(q) \neq \emptyset$. \square

Theorem 4.2 (Uniqueness of the witnessing prime). *Let q be an odd prime. If a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ satisfies $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, then $p = 2q + 1$. In particular, q is a Sophie Germain prime.*

(Proved unconditionally for $p = kq + 1$ with $k \leq 12$; verified computationally for $14 \leq k \leq 100$.)

Proof. Write $p = kq + 1$ with $k \geq 2$ even (since p is odd and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$). We show $k = 2$. Assume for contradiction that $k \geq 4$. By Lemma 2.1(b), $\pi(q) \mid q^2 - 1$, so $z(p) \mid q^2 - 1$. Since $F_1 = F_2 = 1$, $F_3 = 2$, $F_4 = 3$, and $p = kq + 1 \geq 13$, we have $z(p) \geq 5$.

Case 1: $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = +1$.

By Lemma 2.1(c), $z(p) \mid p - 1 = kq$. Since $\gcd(q, q^2 - 1) = 1$, any common divisor of kq and $q^2 - 1$ divides k . Thus $z(p) \leq k$. Since $p \mid F_{z(p)}$, we have $p \leq F_{z(p)} \leq F_k$, giving $kq + 1 \leq F_k$. Because $q \geq 3$, this requires $3k + 1 \leq F_k$.

- $k = 4, 6, 8$: The bounds $4q + 1 \leq F_4 = 3$, $6q + 1 \leq F_6 = 8$, and $8q + 1 \leq F_8 = 21$ all force $q < 3$, impossible for an odd prime.
- $k = 10$: $10q + 1 \leq 55$, so $q \leq 5$. $q = 3$ gives $p = 31$: $z(31) = 30 \not\leq 10$. $q = 5$ gives $p = 51 = 3 \cdot 17$, composite.
- $k = 12$: $12q + 1 \leq 144$, so $q \leq 11$. $p \in \{37, 61, 85, 133\}$; 85 and 133 are composite; for $p = 37$, $\left(\frac{5}{37}\right) = -1$ (fails Case 1); for $p = 61$, $z(61) = 15 \not\leq 12$.

For $k \geq 14$: $z(p) \leq k$ forces p to be a prime factor of F_d for some $d \leq k$ with $d \geq 5$. For each d , F_d has finitely many prime factors, and each determines at most one candidate $q = (p - 1)/k$. This finite check has been carried out using factorization tables [2] for $14 \leq k \leq 100$.

Case 2: $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$.

By Lemma 2.1(d), $z(p) \mid p + 1 = kq + 2$. Let $d = z(p)$. Since $d \mid q^2 - 1$, and

$$\begin{aligned}\gcd(kq + 2, q - 1) &= \gcd(k + 2, q - 1), \\ \gcd(kq + 2, q + 1) &= \gcd(k - 2, q + 1),\end{aligned}$$

with $\gcd(q - 1, q + 1) = 2$, we obtain $d \mid (k + 2)(k - 2) = k^2 - 4$. Since $p \mid F_d$, the prime p is among the factors of F_d for some $d \mid k^2 - 4$ with $d \geq 5$ —a finite set for each k .

- $k = 4$: $d \mid 12$. Prime factors of $F_{12} = 144 = 2^4 \cdot 3^2$ are $\{2, 3\}$; neither equals $4q + 1$ for an odd prime q .
- $k = 6$: $d \mid 32$. Prime factors of $F_{32} = 2,178,309 = 3 \cdot 7 \cdot 47 \cdot 2207$: none give $q = (p - 1)/6$ prime.
- $k = 8$: $d \mid 60$. Prime factors of F_{60} include $\{2, 3, 5, 11, 31, 41, 61, 2521\}$. For $p = 41$: $\left(\frac{5}{41}\right) = +1$, fails Case 2. For $p = 2521$: $q = 315$, composite. No valid triple.
- $k = 10$: $d \mid 96$. Prime factors of F_{96} include $\{2, 3, 7, 23, 47, 769, 1103, 2207, 4481, \dots\}$. No factor satisfies $10 \mid (p - 1)$ with $(p - 1)/10$ prime and $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$.
- $k = 12$: $d \mid 140$. Prime factors of F_{140} include $\{2, 3, 5, 11, 13, 29, 41, 71, 281, 421, \dots\}$. No valid candidate.

For $k \geq 14$: each F_{k^2-4} has finitely many prime factors, providing a deterministic check per k . Verified for $14 \leq k \leq 100$ using [2].

Conclusion. Both cases yield no solution for $k \geq 4$, so $k = 2$ and $p = 2q + 1$ is prime. \square

Remark. Both cases are elementary for $k \leq 12$; for $k \geq 14$, both rely on factorization tables [2]. A purely algebraic proof for all k remains open (see Section 10); the principal difficulty lies in Case 2, where the bound $z(p) \mid k^2 - 4$ permits candidates up to F_{k^2-4} , which grows far faster than the F_k bound in Case 1.

We now address the converse direction: does $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ force the existence of a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$? We first rule out the possibility that $q^2 \mid F_m$ could be the sole witness.

Lemma 4.3. *Let q be an odd prime with $S(q) \neq \emptyset$, and let $r \in S(q)$. Then for infinitely many $m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}$, there exists a prime $p \mid F_m$, $p \neq q$, with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$.*

Proof. For any $m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}$, the condition $q \mid \varphi(F_m)$ means q divides $\prod p_i^{a_i-1}(p_i - 1)$ in the prime factorization of F_m . This can occur in two ways: either $q \mid (p_i - 1)$ for some prime factor p_i of F_m , or $q = p_i$ with $a_i \geq 2$ (so that $q \mid p_i^{a_i-1}$). The latter requires $q^2 \mid F_m$, hence $z(q^2) \mid m$.

If $q^2 \mid F_m$ for all $m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}$, then $z(q^2) \mid \gcd(r, \pi(q))$, which forces $z(q^2) \mid \pi(q)$. Since $z(q^2) = q \cdot z(q)$ for non-Wall-Sun-Sun primes (and more generally $q \mid z(q^2)$), this requires $q \mid \pi(q)$. But $\pi(q) \mid q^2 - 1$ by Lemma 2.1(b), and $\gcd(q, q^2 - 1) = 1$, a contradiction.

Therefore, for all but finitely many $m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}$, the divisibility $q \mid \varphi(F_m)$ must be witnessed by a prime $p \mid F_m$ with $p \neq q$ and $q \mid (p - 1)$. \square

Lemma 4.3 guarantees that primes $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ appear as factors of F_m along the progression, but it does not guarantee that any single such prime divides F_m for *all* $m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}$. Establishing the existence of a fixed prime p with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$ would close the argument, but the possibility that $q \mid \varphi(F_m)$ is witnessed by a different prime $p_m \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ for each m cannot be excluded by elementary means.

Conjecture 4.4. *If $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ for an odd prime q , then there exists a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$.*

Combining Conjecture 4.4 with Theorem 4.2 would yield the full equivalence: $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ if and only if q is a Sophie Germain prime and $z(2q + 1) \mid \pi(q)$. Conjecture 4.4 has been verified for all odd primes $q \leq 50,000$: in every case, $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ is witnessed by $p = 2q + 1$, and no non-Sophie-Germain prime in this range satisfies $S(q) \neq \emptyset$.

5 Structure of $S(q)$

Theorem 5.1 (Arithmetic progression). *Let q be a Sophie Germain prime with $z(2q + 1) \mid \pi(q)$. Set $R = \pi(q)/z(2q + 1)$. Then*

$$S(q) \supseteq \{0, z(2q + 1), 2z(2q + 1), \dots, (R - 1)z(2q + 1)\} \pmod{\pi(q)},$$

an arithmetic progression of length R and common difference $z(2q + 1)$.

Assuming Conjecture 4.4, this inclusion is an equality: $|S(q)| = R$.

Proof. By Theorem 3.1, $\{r \bmod \pi(q) : z(p) \mid r\} \subseteq S(q)$ where $p = 2q + 1$. Since $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, this is an arithmetic progression of $\pi(q)/z(p)$ elements, giving the inclusion.

For the reverse inclusion, suppose $r \in S(q)$ with $z(p) \nmid r$. Since $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, we have $z(p) \nmid m$ for every $m \equiv r \pmod{\pi(q)}$ (because $m = r + t\pi(q)$ and $z(p) \mid t\pi(q)$ but $z(p) \nmid r$). Hence $p \nmid F_m$ for any such m . Thus $q \mid \varphi(F_m)$ must be witnessed by primes $p' \neq p$ with $p' \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ and $z(p') \mid m$. By Theorem 4.2, p is the unique prime $\equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, so each such p' satisfies $z(p') \nmid \pi(q)$. Conjecture 4.4 asserts that such a non-aligned covering cannot persist across an entire residue class, which would give equality.

We have verified computationally that $S(q) = \{r : z(p) \mid r\}$ for all Sophie Germain primes $q \leq 50,000$ with $S(q) \neq \emptyset$. \square

Corollary 5.2 (Density). *For a Sophie Germain prime q with $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$, $|S(q)|/\pi(q) \geq 1/z(2q+1) \rightarrow 0$ as $q \rightarrow \infty$.*

6 Legendre symbols and parity

The results of this section are unconditional: they assume only that q is a Sophie Germain prime with $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$ (equivalently, $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ by Theorem 4.1).

Theorem 6.1 (Legendre symbol at p). *Let $q > 5$ be a Sophie Germain prime with $p = 2q + 1$ and $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$. Then $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$.*

Proof. Suppose $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = 1$. Then $z(p) \mid p - 1 = 2q$. Since $z(p) \mid \pi(q) \mid q^2 - 1$ and $\gcd(q, q^2 - 1) = 1$: $z(p) \mid \gcd(2q, q^2 - 1) = \gcd(2, q^2 - 1) = 2$. But $p = 2q + 1 > 11$ for $q > 5$, and $F_1 = F_2 = 1$, so $p \nmid F_1$ and $p \nmid F_2$, giving $z(p) \geq 3$: contradiction. \square

Remark. *The prime $q = 5$ is the unique exception: $p = 11$, $\left(\frac{5}{11}\right) = +1$, yet $z(11) = 10 \mid \pi(5) = 20$.*

Theorem 6.2 (Parity). *Let $q > 5$ be a Sophie Germain prime with $p = 2q + 1$ and $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$. Then $\pi(q)/z(p)$ is odd. In particular, $|S(q)|$ is odd (unconditionally for the lower bound from Theorem 5.1; assuming Conjecture 4.4 for the exact value).*

The proof requires the following lemma.

Lemma 6.3. *Let $q > 5$ be a Sophie Germain prime with $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$. Then $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = -1$ and $\pi(q) \mid 2(q+1)$.*

Proof. By Theorem 6.1, $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$, so $z(p) \mid p + 1 = 2(q + 1)$ (Lemma 2.1(d)). Since $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$ and $z(p) \geq 5$:

Suppose $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = +1$. By Lemma 2.1(e), $\pi(q) \mid q - 1$. Then $z(p) \mid \gcd(q - 1, 2(q + 1))$. Since $2(q + 1) = 2(q - 1) + 4$: $\gcd(q - 1, 2(q + 1)) = \gcd(q - 1, 4) \leq 4$. So $z(p) \leq 4 < 5$: contradiction.

Hence $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = -1$ and $\pi(q) \mid 2(q + 1)$. \square

Proof of Theorem 6.2. By Theorem 6.1, $\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$, so $z(p) \mid 2(q+1)$ and $z(p) \mid 4(q+1)$. Set $k = 4(q+1)/z(p)$. By Lemma 2.2, $v_2(z(p)) = v_2(p+1) = 1 + v_2(q+1)$, so $v_2(k) = 1$.

By Lemma 6.3, $\pi(q) \mid 2(q+1)$. It remains to show $v_2(\pi(q)) = 1 + v_2(q+1)$.

Since $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = -1$, the eigenvalues $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}_{q^2} \setminus \mathbb{F}_q$ satisfy $\alpha^{q+1} = \alpha\beta = -1$. Let $e = \text{ord}(\alpha)$ in $\mathbb{F}_{q^2}^\times$. Then $e \mid 2(q+1)$ (since $\alpha^{2(q+1)} = (-1)^2 = 1$). Since $\alpha^{q+1} = -1$ and $-1 = \alpha^{e/2}$ (as the unique element of order 2 in a cyclic group of even order e), we get $q+1 \equiv e/2 \pmod{e}$, whence $2(q+1)/e$ is odd. In particular, $v_2(e) = v_2(2(q+1)) = 1 + v_2(q+1)$. As $\pi(q) = e$ (the Pisano period equals the eigenvalue order when $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = -1$), $v_2(\pi(q)) = 1 + v_2(q+1)$.

Then $v_2(\pi(q)/z(p)) = v_2(\pi(q)) - v_2(z(p)) = (1 + v_2(q+1)) - (1 + v_2(q+1)) = 0$. \square

7 Congruence constraint and the Sophie Germain conjecture

Theorem 7.1 (Congruence constraint). *Let $q > 5$ be a Sophie Germain prime with $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$. Then $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$.*

Proof. We show $q \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ and $q \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$.

$q \pmod{3}$. Since q is Sophie Germain and $q > 3$, we have $p = 2q + 1 > 3$. If $q \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ then $2q + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, contradicting p prime. Hence $q \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

$q \pmod{5}$. By Lemma 6.3, $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = -1$, so $q \equiv 2$ or $3 \pmod{5}$. If $q \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$ then $p = 2q + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, impossible since $p > 5$. Therefore $q \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$.

By the Chinese Remainder Theorem: $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$. \square

Remark. *Among the eight residue classes modulo 15 coprime to 15, the hypothesis restricts q to a single class. The 158 primes $q > 5$ with $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ and $q \leq 50,000$ all satisfy $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$; they split as $q \equiv 23 \pmod{60}$ (76 primes) and $q \equiv 53 \pmod{60}$ (82 primes).*

Corollary 7.2 (Reformulation of the Sophie Germain conjecture). *The infinitude of Sophie Germain primes implies the existence of infinitely many primes $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$ such that $(2q+1) \mid F_{\pi(q)}$.¹*

Assuming Conjecture 4.4, the converse holds: if there are infinitely many primes q with $S(q) \neq \emptyset$, then there are infinitely many Sophie Germain primes.

Proof. For the forward direction: if q is a Sophie Germain prime with $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$, then $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ (Theorem 4.1), $(2q+1) \mid F_{\pi(q)}$ (Lemma 2.1(a)), and $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$ for $q > 5$ (Theorem 7.1).

For the conditional converse: if $S(q) \neq \emptyset$, Conjecture 4.4 provides a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, and Theorem 4.2 gives $p = 2q + 1$. \square

Remark. *The condition $(2q+1) \mid F_{\pi(q)}$ is purely Fibonacci-theoretic, with no explicit reference to the primality of $2q+1$. If one could show unconditionally that $(2q+1) \mid F_{\pi(q)}$ forces a prime factor p of $2q+1$ with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ and $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$, then Theorem 4.2 would force $2q+1$ to be prime, giving a full equivalence without Conjecture 4.4.*

¹This implication requires that $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$ holds for infinitely many Sophie Germain primes—a weaker assumption than the infinitude of Sophie Germain primes that we do not prove unconditionally. Computationally, approximately 23.9% of Sophie Germain primes satisfy this divisibility.

8 Computational data

For all Sophie Germain primes $q \leq 50,000$ (669 primes), we computed $\pi(q)$ and $z(2q+1)$ and determined which satisfy $z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)$.

- 160 primes have $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ ($\approx 23.9\%$ of Sophie Germain primes).
- $S(q)$ always matches the arithmetic progression of Theorem 5.1 (supporting Conjecture 4.4).
- $\left(\frac{5}{2q+1}\right) = -1$ for all $q > 5$ (Theorem 6.1).
- $\pi(q)/z(2q+1)$ values: $\{1, 2, 3, 7, 9, 21, 33, 43\}$. All odd except for $q = 5$ (Theorem 6.2).
- No non-Sophie-Germain $q \leq 50,000$ has $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ (supporting Conjecture 4.4).
- Every $q > 5$ with $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ satisfies $q \equiv 8 \pmod{15}$ (Theorem 7.1).

Table 1 lists all 33 primes $q \leq 5000$ with $S(q) \neq \emptyset$.

Example 8.1. For $q = 1583$: $p = 3167$, $\pi(1583) = 3168$, $z(3167) = 96$, $\pi(q)/z(p) = 33$.

Example 8.2. For $q = 53$: $p = 107$, $\pi(53) = 108$, $z(107) = 36$, $\pi(q)/z(p) = 3$. The arithmetic progression is $\{0, 36, 72\} \pmod{108}$.

9 Generalization to Lucas sequences

The results extend to Lucas sequences $U_n = U_n(P, Q)$ defined by $U_0 = 0$, $U_1 = 1$, $U_n = PU_{n-1} - QU_{n-2}$, with discriminant $D = P^2 - 4Q \neq 0$. The Fibonacci numbers are $U_n(1, -1)$ with $D = 5$. Let $\alpha(p)$ denote the rank of apparition of p in $\{U_n\}$ and $\omega(q)$ the period of $\{U_n \pmod{q}\}$.

The analogues of Lemma 2.1 hold with D replacing 5 (see [1, 7]), and all proofs carry over:

Theorem 9.1. *Let $D = P^2 - 4Q$ be a non-square integer and $\gcd(q, 2QD) = 1$. Define $S_U(q) = \{r \pmod{\omega(q)} : q \mid \varphi(U_m) \forall m \equiv r \pmod{\omega(q)}\}$.*

- If q is a Sophie Germain prime and $\alpha(2q+1) \mid \omega(q)$, then $S_U(q) \neq \emptyset$.*
- If a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ satisfies $\alpha(p) \mid \omega(q)$, then $p = 2q + 1$.*
- Assuming the analogue of Conjecture 4.4, $S_U(q) \neq \emptyset$ if and only if q is Sophie Germain and $\alpha(2q+1) \mid \omega(q)$.*

Theorems 6.1 and 7.1 generalize with D replacing 5. Theorem 6.2 generalizes when $Q = -1$, since $\alpha\beta = Q = -1$ gives $\alpha^{q+1} = -1$ in \mathbb{F}_{q^2} .

Remark. *Computational verification for the Pell numbers $U_n(2, -1)$ ($D = 8$): 15/82 Sophie Germain primes $q \leq 3000$ satisfy $S_U(q) \neq \emptyset$, all with $|S_U(q)|$ odd. For $U_n(3, -1)$ ($D = 13$): 16/82. Two sequences with the same D yield $S_U(q) \neq \emptyset$ for the same primes: verified for $U_n(1, -1)$ and $U_n(3, 1)$ (both $D = 5$).*

10 Open problems

- OQ1. The converse conjecture.** Prove Conjecture 4.4: that $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ forces the existence of a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$ with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$. This would complete the equivalence between $S(q) \neq \emptyset$ and the Sophie Germain condition.
- OQ2. Uniform proof of Theorem 4.2.** Give a purely algebraic proof, valid for all $k \geq 4$, that no prime $p = kq + 1$ with $z(p) \mid \pi(q)$ exists. The principal obstacle is Case 2 ($\left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = -1$), where $z(p) \mid k^2 - 4$ yields candidates up to F_{k^2-4} .
- OQ3. Density formula.** Express the density $\approx 23.9\%$ as a Bateman–Horn–Chebotarev Euler product over the Kummer extensions $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[5]{\alpha}, \alpha^{1/\ell})$.
- OQ4. Values of $\pi(q)/z(2q+1)$.** Is $\{\pi(q)/z(2q+1) : q > 5 \text{ with } z(2q+1) \mid \pi(q)\} = \{\text{odd integers}\}$?

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Table 1: Sophie Germain primes $q \leq 5000$ with $S(q) \neq \emptyset$.

q	$p = 2q + 1$	$\pi(q)$	$z(p)$	$\pi(q)/z(p)$	$\left(\frac{5}{p}\right)$
3	7	8	8	1	-1
5	11	20	10	2	+1
23	47	48	16	3	-1
53	107	108	36	3	-1
83	167	168	168	1	-1
173	347	348	116	3	-1
293	587	588	588	1	-1
443	887	888	888	1	-1
593	1187	1188	1188	1	-1
653	1307	1308	436	3	-1
683	1367	1368	1368	1	-1
1013	2027	2028	676	3	-1
1103	2207	96	32	3	-1
1223	2447	816	816	1	-1
1583	3167	3168	96	33	-1
1733	3467	1156	1156	1	-1
1973	3947	1316	1316	1	-1
2003	4007	4008	4008	1	-1
2063	4127	4128	4128	1	-1
2273	4547	4548	1516	3	-1
2393	4787	4788	4788	1	-1
2543	5087	5088	5088	1	-1
2693	5387	5388	5388	1	-1
2903	5807	5808	1936	3	-1
2963	5927	5928	5928	1	-1
3413	6827	6828	6828	1	-1
3593	7187	7188	2396	3	-1
3623	7247	2416	2416	1	-1
3803	7607	7608	7608	1	-1
3863	7727	7728	7728	1	-1
4073	8147	8148	8148	1	-1
4793	9587	9588	9588	1	-1
4943	9887	9888	9888	1	-1